

Educational resources for the retraining of technical stakeholders

1. Introduction

The educational resources of the In Silico World project aim to train or retrain different key groups in the development and use of in silico models in the medical field. One of these key groups is the group employees in industry that have a background in a technical discipline as mathematics or engineering. Concrete lecture material was developed in the format of a mini-course that contains three important topics in the field of in silico medicine. A shortened version of the lecture material was tested by a participant group. Its impact was then evaluated based on a pre- and post-questionnaire, on the one hand, and an in-depth analysis of the pre-defined learning goals, on the other hand. Based on the results, recommendations on the further use and optimization of the lecture material are formulated.

2. Methods

While many topics related to in silico medicine are of interest and educational resources to retrain technically skilled employees is limited, a selection of topics was first of all made by determining intended learning outcomes for the considered participant group at the initial stage. In order to develop educational resources, a mini-course was composed. This mini-course contains three modules, each on a different topic, with some of them being subdivided into two parts. The mini-course aims to make the participants familiar with some basic concepts of in silico modeling in medicine and get a view on the state-of-the-art research. An overview of the considered topics in the mini-course, with the subdivision in parts, and the total duration of each module can be found in table 1. A description of the different modules of the mini-course can be found in appendix A.

Table 1: Overview of the topics and the duration for the modules of the developed mini-course.

Module	Topic	Duration full version (min.)	Duration short version (min.)
1	Regulatory aspects	25	25
2	Reliable measurement input	60	24
	VVUQ: hands-on (video + hands-on)	25 + 70	25 + 10
3	Agent-based models	60	25

In order to collect data and feedback on the composed lecture material, a test version of the mini-course was composed based on a selection of fragments from the video recordings. This selection allows the participants to grasp the main concepts of the lecture in a limited time frame. Next to the selection of fragments, the test version included a pre- and post-questionnaire, as well as an evaluation form after each topic of the mini-course. The total time of the test version was estimated at two hours and 15 minutes. This short version was tested by four participants, working in industry and having a background in biomedical or mechanical engineering.

The pre- and post-questionnaire assessed how aware the participants were on different concepts related to in silico medicine and to which extent they agreed to statements that expressed the potential added value of this domain before and after going through the lecture material, by selecting one of five predefined categories. The categories were not aware, slightly aware, moderately aware, very aware and extremely aware for the questions and strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree and

strongly agree for the statements. Those categories were translated into a numerical score, ranging from one to five. A histogram of the given scores was made for the answers of the pre- and post-questionnaire as well as the difference in pre- and post-score per participant.

Next to the data analysis based on the questionnaires, an in-depth analysis was performed as well. In the evaluation forms, the participants were asked to indicate the three key aspects they wanted to take home. By relating these aspects to the learning goals of each module, an indication was found of the extent to which the learning goals were effectively achieved. Moreover, the stakeholders had the possibility to include written feedback in the form as well.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Analysis of questionnaires

While some variation in the scores given to the different statements was found as well, a clear tendency towards the highest scores was observed, in the histograms as well as in the average values. This indicates a strong initial believe in the potential added value of in silico medicine. The fact that the considered participants voluntarily decided to participate might of course impose an intrinsic bias to the initial interest in the topic.

When comparing the average results of the pre- and post-questionnaire, an increase in the average score is seen for most of the questions. For three questions, a status quo was obtained. The status quo of related to computational mechanics, pharmacokinetic and molecular models is in line with the expectations as this content was not explicitly discussed in the considered mini-course. The largest increases in awareness are observed for artificial intelligence, agent-based models and verification. While artificial intelligence is not elaborately discussed in the mini-course, the increased awareness on agent-based model and verification is expected to result from the lecture material in module two and three.

Figure 1: (a) Mean scores of the questions in the pre- and post-questionnaire regarding the perceived awareness of various in silico medicine concepts. (b) Mean scores of the extent of agreement to the statements in the pre- and post-questionnaire.

The participant-specific differences between the pre- and post-questionnaire in general indicate either a status quo or slight increase in the given score. Only in a single case, the awareness was perceived to be lower after going through the lecture material. The participant-specific results illustrate that not only on average, but also on an individual level, a quite consistent increase was observed (see appendix B).

While a major increase in the perceived knowledge remains absent, an overall increase in the participant awareness was observed, in particular for those concepts that were explicitly addressed and/or where the participants indicated a lower prior awareness. The test version of the mini-course, therefore, shows that the lecture material can advance the awareness of in silico medicine concepts. Of course, following the complete mini-course is expected to further enhance this effect, as grasping the full story might help to build up knowledge in a more coherent manner.

While the interest in following these courses was not directly assessed, the extent of agreement gives an indication of the participants' believe in the potential added value of integrating in silico modeling in medicine. The initial believe illustrated already a high score. Despite one participant indicating a slightly decreased score, the spread in score did not change and the same high categories were selected in the post-questionnaire. This indicates that all participants are (strongly) convinced in the added value of in silico medicine. This group of participants is, therefore, expected to be motivated to further deepen their knowledge by follow more in depth courses and, thus, continue their education.

3.2. In-depth analysis of learning goals

The extent to which the learning goals could be identified in the key aspects provided by the participants, is illustrated in figure 2. The height of the bars indicate the fraction of participants that provided key aspects that could be related to a specific learning goal (see appendix A). The color of the bars shows an *a priori* identification of the extent to which the learning goals were covered in the test version of the lecture material. Green, orange and red, respectively, refer to a learning goal that is well, moderately or not covered in the test version.

Figure 2: Frequency of indication of learning of (a) module, (b) module 2 part 1, (c) module 2 part 2 and (d) module 3. The height of the colored bar indicates the fraction of participants that provided key aspects related to the considered learning goals. The color of the bar as well as the background indicates how well the learning goal was covered in the test version of the lecture material, with green, orange and red respectively referring to well, moderately and not covered.

While the relation between the provided key aspects and the learning goals is subject to interpretation and the frequency of indication depends on the number of learning goals for each modules, the analysis gives an estimation of the combined effect of the aspects that are of interest to the participants and the information that the participant retains from the lecture material.

Overall, most of the well or moderately covered learning goals were indicated in the key aspects of, at least, part of the participants. The frequency of indication and its relation to the amount of attention that was spend to the goal in the test version of the mini-course was, however, variable. Some of the learning goals that were expected to be well covered in the short version of the lecture material, were indeed frequently indicated in the key aspects of the participants. This confirms that, at least, part of the content of the lecture material was effectively grasped by the participants. Surprisingly, some of the learning goals that were only moderately or not covered in the test version were still (frequently) identified, while some of the well covered learning goals were not (often) indicated. On the one hand, this might indicate that a learning goal should be addressed more explicitly in order to ensure that the participants grasp the envisioned content, in particular for those goals that have a lower frequency of indication than expected. On the other hand, this effect could also be related to the interest of the participants and, therefore, provide information on the topics the participants are interested in, which can contribute to the further optimization of the lecture material.

First of all, learning goals that were considered to be well covered in the test version and that were often indicated as key aspects should retain their importance in an optimized version of the mini-course. Also learning goals that were frequently indicated, while the goal was only moderately covered, do not imply an immediate change of the lecture material. In the complete mini-course, more attention is already provided to the considered goal, which is expected to be sufficient. Nevertheless, these topics are expected to be of specific interest to the participants. In more specialized or elaborate courses, it could, therefore, be relevant to provide more in-depth information on those topics.

Learning goals that were only indicated to a limited extent, compared to the *a priori* expectations, deserve additional attention in the optimization of the lecture material. Indeed, the first stage is to reconsider the importance of the learning goal. If the learning goal is still considered to be important, than the way the content is provided should be reconsidered. Making the mini-course more interactive or adding more motivating examples could contribute to help the participant in grasping the content.

Moreover, it should be noted that the current evaluation format, i.e. asking for three key aspects, is prone to interpretation. Therefore, an assessment with multiple choice questions could provide valuable objective information on the grasped knowledge of the participants.

4. Outlook

Based on a quantitative analysis, the effect of the lecture material on the awareness of in silico medicine and believe in its potential added value is promising. While the size of the test group was very limited, these results indicate that a small amount of lecture material already has an impact.

Longer and more specific courses are needed in a next step to further enhance their knowledge of the use, applications and potential added value of in silico modeling in medicine.

The in-depth analysis indicates to which extent the learning goals were considered to be key aspects by the participants. This gives combined information of the interest of the participants and how well they grasped the learning goals. It is strongly recommended to include this information in further optimization of the lecture material, in particular for those learning goals that resulted in a lower frequency of identification compared to the initial expectations.

The written feedback identified that mainly the lecture material on regulatory aspects was of great value to the participants. Therefore, an extension of this module with some hands-on examples are recommended.

Moreover a short self-assessment after following the mini-course could help the stakeholder to assess their knowledge on the discussed topics in a more objective way, compared to the questionnaire where only their perception of awareness was queried. As a proof of concept, some assessment-questions were already implemented to showcase the suggested improvement of the lecture material.

Appendix A – Modules of mini-course

Module 1: Regulatory aspects

With the perspective to integrate in silico medicine in the process of diagnosis, treatment development and treatment selection, a regulatory framework is unavoidable. This course module provides an overview of the state-of-the-art regarding the regulatory framework and the aspects that are still lacking.

An overview of the learning goals is given below.

1. Illustrate the importance of regulatory pathways;
2. Identify the main regulatory authorities in the United States and the EU in the framework of biomedical in silico models;
3. Classify a computational model as digital twin or as in silico trial methodology and formulate the implications on the required regulatory pathways;
4. Formulate which standard is currently used to assess the credibility of a computational model;
5. Identify relevant regulatory guides for a given application including a biomedical in silico model.

Module 2

Part A: Reliable measurement input

As in silico medicine models often require experimental or clinical measurements as input, the outcome of these models depends on these measurements. The importance of awareness of the reliability of the measurement input and its effect on the outcome is illustrated based on the C4Bio project.

An overview of the learning goals is given below.

1. Outline the importance of reliable measurement input in in silico modeling;
2. Distinguish between input variability and input uncertainty;
3. Identify and situate sources of uncertainty in the process of in silico modeling;
4. Propose measures to account for the uncertainty on the measurement input, in the process of in silico modeling;
5. Illustrate the impact of measurement input uncertainty based on state-of-the-art research;
6. Integrate uncertainty quantification in the development process of reliable in silico models.

Part B: VVUQ hands-on

In the framework of in silico modeling is not only the technical development of the models essential, but also its evaluation. This evaluation comprises a combination of verification, validation and uncertainty quantification of the model. In this course module, these concepts are introduced and the participants will practice them based on concept questions and apply them in an example model of an aortic aneurysm.

An overview of the learning goals is given below.

1. Distinguish between Clinical Trials and In Silico Clinical Trials and comprehend their respective advantages and disadvantages;
2. Summarize the different steps listed in the ASME V&V40 document;
3. Identify the question of interest, the context of use and the model risk for a specific example of a computational model within the framework of in silico medicine;
4. Classify credibility activities of a computational model into verification or validation;
5. Execute code and calculation verification;
6. Analyze and interpret the results of an uncertainty and sensitivity analysis;
7. Illustrate model form selection of a computational model;
8. Understand the concept of comparators in the context of model validation.

Module 3: Agent-based models

While many in silico medicine models represent the aggregated behavior of a tissue or body part, an agent-based models utilizes an alternative approach, where individual agents and their mutual interaction play a central role. The course module explains the general model principles, their benefits, and illustrates the modeling technique with potential applications.

An overview of the learning goals is given below.

1. Formulate the general working principle of an agent-based model;
2. Clarify the role and the main features of an agent in agent-based models;
3. Formulate advantages and disadvantages of a bottom-up and top-down modeling approach;
4. Relate the use of agent-based modeling to a bottom-up approach in in silico modeling;
5. Illustrate the use of agent-based models with a state-of-the-art research example.

Appendix B – Participant-specific results

Question 1: Computational mechanics

Figure B1: (a) Histogram of the difference between the score on awareness question 1 of the pre- and post-questionnaire per participant. (b) Histogram of the scores given by each participant to awareness question 1 in the pre- and post-questionnaire.

Question 2: Multiscale modeling

Figure B2: (a) Histogram of the difference between the score on awareness question 2 of the pre- and post-questionnaire per participant. (b) Histogram of the scores given by each participant to awareness question 2 in the pre- and post-questionnaire.

Question 3: Artificial intelligence

Figure B3: (a) Histogram of the difference between the score on awareness question 3 of the pre- and post-questionnaire per participant. (b) Histogram of the scores given by each participant to awareness question 3 in the pre- and post-questionnaire.

Question 4: Pharmacokinetic models

Figure B4: (a) Histogram of the difference between the score on awareness question 4 of the pre- and post-questionnaire per participant. (b) Histogram of the scores given by each participant to awareness question 4 in the pre- and post-questionnaire.

Question 5: (Bayesian) network models

Figure B5: (a) Histogram of the difference between the score on awareness question 5 of the pre- and post-questionnaire per participant. (b) Histogram of the scores given by each participant to awareness question 5 in the pre- and post-questionnaire.

Question 6: Agent based models

Figure B6: (a) Histogram of the difference between the score on awareness question 6 of the pre- and post-questionnaire per participant. (b) Histogram of the scores given by each participant to awareness question 6 in the pre- and post-questionnaire.

Question 7: Molecular modeling

Figure B7: (a) Histogram of the difference between the score on awareness question 7 of the pre- and post-questionnaire per participant. (b) Histogram of the scores given by each participant to awareness question 7 in the pre- and post-questionnaire.

Question 8: Uncertainty quantification

Figure B8: (a) Histogram of the difference between the score on awareness question 8 of the pre- and post-questionnaire per participant. (b) Histogram of the scores given by each participant to awareness question 8 in the pre- and post-questionnaire.

Question 9: Verification

Figure B9: (a) Histogram of the difference between the score on awareness question 9 of the pre- and post-questionnaire per participant. (b) Histogram of the scores given by each participant to awareness question 9 in the pre- and post-questionnaire.

Question 10: Validation

Figure B10: (a) Histogram of the difference between the score on awareness question 10 of the pre- and post-questionnaire per participant. (b) Histogram of the scores given by each participant to awareness question 10 in the pre- and post-questionnaire.

Statement 1: Accelerate adoption of new medical device or treatment

Figure B11: (a) Histogram of the difference between the score on statement 1 of the pre- and post-questionnaire per participant. (b) Histogram of the scores given by each participant to statement 1 in the pre- and post-questionnaire.

Statement 2: Decrease number of clinical trials conducted on humans or animals

Figure B12: (a) Histogram of the difference between the score on statement 2 of the pre- and post-questionnaire per participant. (b) Histogram of the scores given by each participant to statement 2 in the pre- and post-questionnaire.

Statement 3: Decrease cost to develop medical device or treatment

Figure B13: (a) Histogram of the difference between the score on statement 3 of the pre- and post-questionnaire per participant. (b) Histogram of the scores given by each participant to statement 3 in the pre- and post-questionnaire.